

Report on the final implementation of key selected post-processing,
analytics and visualisation applications and main outcomes

Deliverable D5.3

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1 Abstract /publishable summary

In the ESiWACE Center of Excellence the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) provides a data model that manages datasets in virtual containers with their metadata.

Building on this work, a Python client has been developed for building pipelines consisting of ESDM-enabled post-processing, analytics and visualisation (PAV) applications. Among these PAV applications the key selected ones are: Ophidia, an open source solution for the analysis of multi-dimensional data, mainly targeted at climate science applications; CDO, a collection of command line operators to manipulate and analyse climate and weather data; ParaView, a widely used application for interactive 3D rendering and analysis of large data sets. The Ophidia framework has been improved in various ways, in particular with respect to parallel I/O, handling of non-regular grids and in-flight analytics. For the CDOs we have shown that a significant performance improvement can be obtained using GPUs. ParaView now supports arbitrary grids, such as those of the ICON, IFS, and FESOM models, the components of the DestinE digital twins. With the newly developed YAVIZ interface, it can also be used for online (in-transit) diagnostics and visualization with models that use the YAC coupler (currently the ICON model, we are working on YAC-support in FESOM). Furthermore, we have developed Python bindings for YAC, so now any Python based analysis (e.g. machine learning codes) can be applied as online analysis to the fields of the ICON model.

2 Conclusion & Results

The main results and conclusions from the final implementation of the selected PAV applications can be summarised as:

- We extended the PAV applications to support the model grids of the ESiWACE2 flagship models.
- With ESDM-PAV we provide a common interface for combining various post-processing tools in one tool-chain. Providing a Python library allows to exploit the interface from well-known solutions for data science such as Jupyter Notebooks.
- By making use of standard interfaces, such as an ESDM-enabled netCDF library, it was easy to integrate ESDM in PAV applications.
- For most online analysis and visualization tasks, in-transit processing is the way forward, as analyses can be performed with a fraction of the processes on separate nodes.
- Extensions for in-flight analytics (i.e., applying simple operations while moving data from the storage to the compute node) provided interesting results. Tested within the Ophidia framework allowed to obtain a noticeable reduction in the analysis execution time.
- By providing a python interface for the YAC coupler, we pave the path for a multitude of online diagnosis approaches.
- More advanced concepts about the execution order and memory layout for the CDOs have been discussed in depth, and are likely to enter future versions of this toolbox.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	–
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	–
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	–

4 Detailed Report on the Deliverable

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) provides a data model that manages datasets in virtual containers with their metadata. The framework was developed in ESiWACE, for further detail see other ESiWACE2 publications, especially deliverable D5.2 (Heidmann et al., 2022) (section 4.2) and D4.1 (Bethke et al., 2021).

A Python client has been developed for building pipelines consisting of (ESDM-enabled) **P**ost-processing, **A**nalytics and **V**isualisation (PAV) applications (see D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021)). Among these PAV applications the key selected ones are: Ophidia, CDO and ParaView.

The Ophidia framework has been improved during the project to fully support parallel I/O from NetCDFv4 and ESDM as well as for handling non-regular grids. The use of in-flight analytics in the framework has been explored, showing promising results. Moreover, the setup of Ophidia has been simplified through the integration in the Spack package manager. We have shown that a significant performance improvement can be obtained using GPUs for CDOs. ParaView now supports arbitrary grids, and can be run as in-transit application with ICON and the YAC coupler. ICON data can be used in Python for in-transit analysis via the YAC coupler.

This deliverable presents the recent developments in Work Package 5 (WP5), since D5.2 was published, and, such, the main activities for the final implementation of the PAV applications. Also, it provides some guidelines and lessons learnt from the work done in WP5 during the ESiWACE2 project. The next subsection contextualizes the main pipelines addressed in ESiWACE2 WP5 and provides an overview on how the PAV applications fit into this picture. The following subsections dive more into the details of the results from the different implementation efforts carried out. The final part of this section highlights some best practices and lesson learnt from this work.

4.1 Overview of the PAV use in the ESM workflow

Figure 1 provides an **overview of the Earth System Model (ESM) workflow** highlighting the components most relevant to the ESiWACE2 project and the work packages addressing these aspects; those in orange

are the blocks where WP5 provided the main contributions. Two different types of workflows have been taken into consideration: batch pipelines of post-processing, analytics and visualisation tasks, and in-situ visualisation pipelines. The two scenarios start both from a ESM simulation, such as one of the flagships model supported by the project (e.g., ICON, IFS, etc.). In the batch processing case, the pipeline is applied on the data produced by the model which can be located on disk and stored in NetCDF or ESDM format, whereas in the in-situ case data is accessed from the HPC nodes where the model is running directly via the model coupler.

Figure 1: High-level Earth System Model workflow and contributions from ESIWACE2 Work Packages. Contributions from WP5 are in orange. The two scenarios explored in the work package are shown in more detail in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

A **typical batch processing pipeline** is presented in Figure 2. This diagram shows some of the key aspects of the workflow, highlighting the contributions from ESIWACE2. The first block in the flow chart represents the configuration of the PAV pipeline, through the definition of a workflow document. The PAV Python module, developed in ESIWACE, can be used to define the tasks of the pipeline and manage its execution on the system. Moreover, the whole PAV pipeline status can be monitored using the PAV Python interface, also in real-time with a graphical format in a Jupyter Notebook. One of the early step in the PAV pipeline execution relates to accessing the datasets, which can be now read from ESDM, besides NetCDF. The Ophidia extensions developed in the project also allow to apply in-flight operations while loading the data from the ESDM data store to the compute nodes. CDO and Ophidia can process different types of grids in parallel: CDO now provides some kernels which can make use of GPUs, while Ophidia now supports also unstructured grids. Data can be then stored in ESDM format by CDO and Ophidia and accessed for visualisation with ParaView, which in turn can now support multiple types of grids and access data from ESDM.

Figure 2: Scenario 1 workflow: PAV pipeline starting from data access to multiple experiments on disk. The left-side of the figure shows the pipeline steps, while the right-side shows the contributions by the ESiWACE2 project.

Figure 3 presents a **typical in-situ visualisation/analysis workflow**. As the in-situ visualisation/analysis is run with the model in the batch mode, most of the work has to be done prior to triggering the model run, and all parameters of a visualisation/analysis need to already be defined when the model is run. Therefore, pre-existing output is used to develop the ParaView Catalyst pipeline. This can - with the extensions to the ParaView CDI reader developed in ESiWACE - now be done with data on arbitrary grids. ParaView Catalyst is later connected via the YAC coupler (with extensions from ESiWACE2) and the YAVIZ visualization connector (developed in ESiWACE2). As YAC supports remaps to arbitrary grids, the choice of the ideal grid for the analysis is part of the configurations of the pipeline. CDO can be used to remap existing output to candidate grids, which can then be used in the pipeline. Standard options here include subsetting the grid (e.g. if a visualisation centered on Europe is planned, the data can be cropped to this region), or if an analysis requires data on lat/lon grid, the model grid can be remapped to lat/lon. As last step in the preparation of the simulation, the ParaView Catalyst pipeline and YAVIZ need to be configured and anchored in the run scripts of the model. Finally, the simulation can be triggered, resulting in images / analysis results on disk.

Figure 3: Scenario 2 workflow: in-situ visualisation. The left-side of the figure shows the pipeline steps, while the right-side shows the contributions from the ESiWACE2 project. YAVIZ is the interface connecting ParaView Catalyst to the YAC coupler of the model. MPMD is the “Multiple Program Multiple Data Execution Model” of the Message Passing Interface for parallel computations.

4.2 ESDM

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM)¹, developed in the context of the ESiWACE CoE, supports applications like climate simulations and weather forecasts to exploit heterogeneous storage resources in a data center. More specifically, ESDM aims to provide parallel I/O for parallel applications, with advanced features to optimize subsequent read accesses. It has been implemented with a standalone API and also provides a NetCDF integration allowing a simple usage in existing applications (Kunkel et al., 2020).

The ESDM-PAV runtime, developed during the ESiWACE2 project, provides the extensions to support Post-processing, Analytics and Visualisation (PAV) needs in the field of climate and weather applications and it integrates the ESDM system for the interaction at the storage layer, although it also supports interactions with regular NetCDF/POSIX based files. It delivers a Python-based interface (the PAV client) to build PAV experiments composed of different tools, such as CDO, Ophidia and ParaView. It integrates the ESDM layer for I/O and in-flight analytics purposes (Elia et al., 2021). The test cases, defined in the next subsection, allowed us to improve the version presented in D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021) by fixing a set of bugs and consolidating the setup process.

In particular, the ESDM-PAV Python client² provides the features to build pipelines of PAV operators and orchestrate their execution on compute nodes (through the ESDM-PAV runtime), as well as monitoring the execution of the pipeline. To this end, a graphical view of the workflow, that can be accessed also via Jupyter Notebooks, is produced by the module and updated iteratively (Elia et al., 2021).

4.2.1 Test cases pipelines

This subsection reports two use cases and provides the corresponding pipeline executed, in order to show how PAV Runtime can be exploited to carry out PAV workflows. These two use cases have been named in the following as “extreme event computation” and “iterative processing” pipelines. The complete pipeline description using the PAV Python client is available in the Appendix.

¹<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

²<https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client>

The pipeline of the first use case aims at evaluating and visualising the “cold spells” in the data. From an implementation point of view it consists in a set of post-processing operations on the variable “Minimum Air Surface Temperature” (concisely `tasmin`) stored in NetCDF files retrieved from the CMIP6 archive and a final visualisation of the results. This use case integrates in a single workflow CDO, Ophidia and ParaView. The second use case shows how the runtime and ESDM-based Ophidia operators implemented in WP4 and WP5 can effectively be used to process datasets stored in ESDM containers. In this case, the scenario considered consists of a model simulation producing data and storing them in an ESDM container as soon as available. In the meanwhile, an instance of the PAV Runtime is periodically checking the container for new data (i.e. probing), starting some analytics operations over the data gathered so far as soon as new data are available (e.g., a new time step of the simulation).

Extreme Events Computation Pipeline

This use case aims at evaluating the ESDM-PAV runtime when using a mixed set of PAV applications: i.e., CDO, Ophidia and ParaView. From a scientific point of view, it computes some indicators related to the “cold spells”, i.e. the periods in which the surface air temperature is constantly at least 5 °C lower than the corresponding climatological average in the past. This pipeline allows to analyse the conditions of an extreme climate event, such as the duration and the frequency of these “cold waves” and how climate change is impacting on their severity.

The workflow processes two input datasets, one for past and one for future projections, and evaluates three metrics related to the “cold spells”: maximum event duration, yearly number and frequency. To test the workflow, we have considered the datasets identified by the following index in the context of CMIP6 archive:

- CMIP6.HighResMIP.MPI-M.MPI-ESM1-2-XR.highresSST-present.r1i1p1f1.day.tasmin.gn
- CMIP6.HighResMIP.MPI-M.MPI-ESM1-2-XR.highresSST-future.r1i1p1f1.day.tasmin.gn

The workflow, shown in Listing 4, is composed by four parts:

1. computation of the climatological averages (using past simulation data);
2. intercomparison between future projections and past data;
3. evaluation of the metrics (analysis);
4. visualisation.

In the first phase (lines 7-29) the workflow evaluates a baseline used for the climate indicators over a historical long-term period. In particular, this baseline consists of the average value for each year using a 5-day sliding window averaged over all the reference period (20 years from 1995 to 2014). Climatological averages are mainly obtained by a chain of CDO operators (`ydaymean`, `runavg`, etc.) applied on the input NetCDF files (line 10) and ends with the load of the intermediate results into Ophidia platform using the operator `OPH_IMPORTNC2` (line 20).

In the second part (lines 30-75), for each year in the considered time period in the future (10 years from 2041 to 2050), an intercomparison between future projections and past climatological averages is evaluated by the operator `OPH_INTERCUBE` (line 48). The control operators `for` and `endfor`, configured in parallel mode (line 35), are used to define the loading of more input NetCDF files concurrently (line 37); the path to each input file is referred as `@source` in the loop; the final operator `OPH_MERGEUBES` concatenates the time series in the same Ophidia datacube (line 69) containing the durations of the cold spell.

The analysis phase (tasks `t5`, `t6`, `t7`, `t8` and `t9`) is carried out by Ophidia operators by evaluating the following indexes:

- Cold Spell Duration Index (CSD): starting from the daily maximum temperature t_{asmin} , the index is the maximum number of days, at intervals of at least 6 days, while t_{asmin} is 5 °C lower than the corresponding climatological average.
- Cold Spell Number (CSN): number of cold spells in a year.
- Cold Spell Frequency (CSF): number of days that contribute to cold spells in a year.

For the last part, Ophidia is used to create three output NetCDF files (tasks $t5e$, $t7e$ and $t9e$) whereas Paraview, called within the script `visualise.sh` (in tasks $t5v$, $t7v$ and $t9v$), is used to show the results.

The output produced with ParaView from the first list of operators (the cold spell duration - CSD, i.e., the max cold spell length in a single year) is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Result from the visualisation of one of the cold spell pipeline results (the CSD index).

The workflow “Cold Spells” has been written in Python by exploiting the client interface of ESDM-PAV named ESDM-PAV Python Client³, so that it is compliant with the PAV experiment schema defined in deliverable D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021).

Figure 5 shows a graphical representation of the workflow obtained by processing ten input NetCDF files produced through the Python client. Note that tasks defined between the operators `for` and `endfor` have been replicated ten times according to the number of input files: each branch is related to a specific input file. The use of the `for` flow control operators allows to easily scale the execution on multiple input files of the dataset (i.e., one for each year) and run independent pipelines of PAV operations in parallel. Actually, we have varied the number of input files in our tests (up to 20) to verify system stability and detect possible performance limits or drawbacks. Our tests confirm that the runtime is stable and allows to scale the execution of multiple tasks. More details on the use of the `for` flow management constructs can be found in deliverable D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021).

³<https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client>

Figure 5: A graphical representation of the pipeline for “Cold Spells” computation.

Iterative Processing Pipeline In this second use case, an analytics pipeline processing the data produced by a simulation model running (potentially) at the same time is considered. The PAV Runtime exploits the control operator `wait`, designed for WP5 to assess data as soon as this is written to the ESDM by the model. It is worth noting that this control operator also supports checking the availability of NetCDF files. More details about these features are presented in D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021). The workflow, shown in Listing 5, consists of a loop containing the following statements:

1. wait for the output data of the current simulation step (i.e., probe for data availability);
2. apply a kernel in-flight to evaluate the spatial maximum and minimum while loading current simulation results;
3. append the new pair (max, min) to output Ophidia datacube.

In this test case scenario, the Ophidia datacube resulting from the third statement (initially empty) will gather the pairs maximum-minimum over the spatial domain for a configurable set of time steps of the simulation data (e.g., a single time step).

The workflow exploits a number of ESDM-PAV operators implemented in deliverable D5.1 (Elia et al., 2021). For instance, the control operators `for` (line 7) and `endfor` (line 65) are used to set up the loop: for each cycle the variable `index` is updated (from 1 to 100 in this case) to consider different simulation periods (line 10).

At the beginning of each cycle, ESDM-PAV Runtime sets some internal parameters (line 12): the indexes `start` and `stop` of the first time step and the last step to be considered in current simulation period, the string `previous` equal to the PID of the last Ophidia cube created (initially the string is empty). These parameters are used to set appropriately the arguments of the other operators in the loop. Note that each simulation period defined by `[start, stop]` consists of 10 time steps. The reserved word `EVAL` is adopted to encircle a numerical expression to be evaluated before assigning the value to the corresponding workflow variable. The control operator `SET` can be used to define variables that are useful for setting task arguments during the pipeline execution. Specifically, the operator allows the user to extend the passing of metadata from a task to a dependent task by linking the outputs of the former to the arguments of the latter. Similarly to other control operators (Elia et al., 2021), the definition of this construct has been inherited from the an operator already support by Ophidia and its interface and implementation has been adapted to address ESDM-PAV runtime requirements.

Then, ESDM-PAV Runtime executes the control operator `wait` (polling phase): workflow execution stops until the data related to the last step of the current simulation period `[start, stop]` is available (line 25), assuming that data are produced neatly along the time dimension; in the meanwhile, the runtime periodically checks for data availability (the polling period is 10 s in this case, line 27). Note that the input dataset `tas` is stored in the ESDM container named `esdm://etas.nc` in this case: since this container also is the output of the task, the value of argument `output` is set to `esdm://etas.nc`.

Upon new simulation results are available, the control operator `if` is executed to select the next operation (line 32). The condition `&index=1` is true only for the first loop, when the initial results are fed into Ophidia platform as a new data cube by using `OPH_IMPORTESDM2` (line 34). For each other loop, data are appended to the previous Ophidia cube (identified by the string `previous`) by `OPH_CONCATESDM2` (line 49). Note that, in both cases, Ophidia applies the in-flight kernel `stat` with the parameter 11 (lines 41-42 and 56-57): this involves the evaluation, while data is being transferred from ESDM to Ophidia, of the minimum and maximum of the selected data (lines 39 and 54), thus loading only this pair of values from the ESDM container instead of all raw data produced during the current simulation period. More details about this new analytical kernels are provided in subsection 4.3. By using the approach adopted in Ophidia to access vector runtime variables, the variable `@start_1` is set to the first time step to be considered in a loop, namely the first element of the variable list set at the beginning of the loop (line 16), whereas `@start` indicates all the list, namely an array. Figure 6 shows a graphical representation of the workflow in three moments of the execution and, in particular, during:

- a) the waiting time for new data from the simulation (polling phase);
- b) the first data loading from simulation output repository;
- c) a data loading after the first one.

The colour of the waiting task is cyan during the polling phase, whereas it becomes green upon the data are available. The colour of task `OPH_IMPORTESDM2` (and `OPH_CONCATESDM2`) is orange during the execution, whereas it is grey in case the control operator `if` does not select the task.

Figure 6: A graphical representation of the workflow “Iterative processing” at different stages: a) waiting for new data available, b) first data loading, c) loading of additional data.

The sample workflow shown in Listing 5 contains only the data reduction executed by the kernel `stat` (see section 4.3.1), anyway additional operations could clearly be performed on the data loaded onto Ophidia platform both during the loop and at the end of procedure. Moreover, intermediate and final results could further be processed by the platform (before the final storage of data on ESDM, line 70). Likewise, other PAV applications, such as CDO and ParaView, could be added at the end of the pipeline.

This test case allowed evaluating the level of integration of the runtime and Ophidia with respect to the ESDM system and the use of in-flight analytical kernels in a "realistic" processing pipeline. Concerning in particular the Ophidia framework, these extensions open the floor to new types of processing pipelines where data can be accessed as soon as available and pre-processed while being loaded into the framework. It is worth mentioning that although the developments tested in this use case target a specific storage middleware (i.e., ESDM) the approach can be generalised to be reused with different storage solutions.

4.3 Ophidia

Ophidia is a CMCC Foundation research effort addressing Big Data challenges for eScience (Fiore et al., 2013). The Ophidia framework is an open source (GPLv3) solution for the analysis of scientific multi-dimensional data, mainly targeted at climate science applications, although it has also been successfully exploited in other scientific domains (e.g., seismology, biology, wildfire monitoring). This section summarises the main extensions carried out during the ESiWACE2 project in order to improve the framework performance and support for ESM data, as well as some results from the test of the key extensions.

4.3.1 Main developments

In the context of the ESiWACE2 project the Ophidia framework has been extended to support new use cases and ESM data; milestone MS5.2 report documents the last release of the software (Budich et al., 2022). The main developments during the project include:

- Extensions to support the integration of the ESDM through the ESDM-NetCDF library;
- New operators integrating directly the ESDM API (more details on this can be found in (Bethke et al., 2021)):
 - `OPH_IMPORTESDM` (with a second improved implementation called `OPH_IMPORTESDM2`) for loading data from a ESDM container into an Ophidia datacube;
 - `OPH_EXPORTESDM` (with a second improved implementation called `OPH_EXPORTESDM2`) for exporting data from an Ophidia datacube into a ESDM container;
 - `OPH_CONCATESDM` (with a second improved implementation called `OPH_CONCATESDM2`) for appending a ESDM container data to an Ophidia datacube;
- Extensions to the ESDM-based import operators to support in-flight analytical kernels. Around 20 kernels have been implemented for supporting subsetting, aggregation and statistical functions (more details on this can be found in (Heidmann et al., 2022)). The last release of the kernels can be found at: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-analytical-kernels>;
- Adaptations to the Ophidia server interface to be fully compliant with the ESDM-PAV experiment schema. Moreover some optimization have been performed to the Ophidia server based on the experience from the PAV runtime;
- Improvements to the NetCDF-based import operators to better support parallel loading (with multi-process/multi-threading) from NetCDFv4 files (based on HDF5). In particular, support for loading data in parallel with multiple threads, besides multiple processes, has been added;

```
{
  "name": "Import",
  "type": "ophidia",
  "operator": "oph_importesdm",
  "arguments": [
    "input=esdm://pressure.nc",
    "measure=pressure",
    "operation=stat",
    "args=101"
  ]
}
```

Listing 1: Example of application of the kernel “stat”

- Extensions to the framework to support non-regular gridded NetCDF datasets. The extension has been successfully tested with most of the models supported by the project (i.e., ICON, IFS);
- Improvements to the Ophidia Python binding (i.e., PyOphidia) for a stronger integration with other Python-based community tools and libraries (e.g., Xarray and Pandas), which have been used in training events organised with WP6.

As mentioned in the previous section, a new kernel has been added to the set of analytical kernels supported by Ophidia for in-flight analysis (Heidmann et al., 2022): the `stat` kernel. This kernel, which can be applied while loading data from an ESDM container using both versions of `OPH_IMPORTESDM` and `OPH_CONCATESDM`, evaluates up to three statistics: maximum, minimum and average. The user can select the specific metrics to be evaluated by setting the argument `args` (a binary mask) of the Ophidia operators as follows:

- 100 means “evaluates the maximum”
- 010 means “evaluates the minimum”
- 001 means “evaluates the average”
- 110 means “evaluates the maximum and the minimum”
- 101 means “evaluates the maximum and the average”
- 011 means “evaluates the minimum and the average”
- 111 means “evaluates the maximum, the minimum and the average”

As for other kernels used for data reduction, instead of raw data the kernel returns only the values of the statistics chosen. The example in Listing 1 shows how to load the maximums and the averages of raw data from an ESDM dataset `esdm://pressure.nc`; the argument `args` has been set to 101.

Moreover, the overall setup procedure of the Ophidia framework has been simplified and the framework has been included in the list of packages available through the Spack package management system (<https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). Spack is a multi-platform package manager that builds and installs multiple versions and configurations of software. This activity aimed to making Ophidia deployment on different HPC systems easier and thus support the portability of the framework. A future activity in this direction will concern the integration of the steps required for updating the Spack configuration into Ophidia's Continuous Integration systems and support the automated software release process.

4.3.2 Performance Evaluation

An experimental evaluation of the main Ophidia extensions for (i) integrating the ESDM interface and (ii) supporting in-flight analytical kernels has been performed to validate the implementation activities and understand their impact in terms of performance.

Test environment

This benchmark has been performed on the testbed environment setup on the Zeus cluster at the CMCC Supercomputing Centre. Zeus is the current CMCC's supercomputer providing 1.2 PetaFlops of peak performance. It is composed of 348 nodes with a total of 12,528 processors and 33.4 TB of main memory. Each node is equipped with 2 Intel Xeon Gold 6154 3.0 GHz processors (18 cores each) and 96 GB of main memory, with Linux CentOS 7.6 used as the operating system. The cluster exploits a GPFS parallel file system with a peak aggregated bandwidth of 80 GB/s. The testbed includes the latest version of the Ophidia framework (v1.7), with all the developments introduced in the previous section, and a setup of the ESDM (latest version from the master github branch⁴). The ESDM backend used for the tests is based on the POSIX file system. For each test presented in the following the Ophidia I/O servers are deployed in an exclusive fashion on the cluster node.

Experiments definition

The goal of this benchmark is two-fold:

1. first it aims at evaluating the performance of the different levels of integration with the ESDM library in the Ophidia framework;
2. secondly it aims at understanding the impact of the in-flight analytics with respect to the approach currently provided by the Ophidia framework.

More specifically, the proposed tests focus on the evaluation of the strong and weak scalability with respect to the Ophidia operators performing data reading rather than writing, since this is typically the most time consuming stage in the overall data analytics workflow.

The measurement of strong scaling is done by testing how the execution time changes with the number of computing units while the data size remains constant. On the other hand, the test for weak scaling is done by increasing both the number of computing units and the data size.

The operators selected for the evaluation can be briefly described as follows:

For the first goal:

- Read data from a ESDM container using the ESDM-NetCDF library again through the OPH_IMPORTNC2 Ophidia operator. In the following this operation will be identified as IMPORTNC + ESDM;
- Read data from an ESDM container directly using the ESDM API through the OPH_IMPORTESDM2 Ophidia operator. In the following this operation will be identified as IMPORTESDM.

For the second one:

- Read data from a ESDM container and then perform a data reduction operation through the OPH_REDUCE Ophidia operator. The two stages of the operations (data loading and reduction) are reported separately to better understand the impact of the different parts. In the following this operation will be identified as IMPORT + REDUCE;
- Read data from an ESDM container and directly apply a data analytics kernel in-flight. This is performed using the OPH_IMPORTESDM2 operator with the support for in-flight analytics. In the following this operation will be identified as IMPORT IN-FLIGHT.

⁴<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

All the described operators have been tested under the same conditions. For each test case, the operators have been run five times and the average execution time has been computed.

Data structure

To run the tests, a dataset of the ESiWACE2 flagship models (i.e., sample files from the ICON model) in NetCDF format has been used as input for the different operators.

The dataset includes a single 2-dimensional (i.e., time \times ncells) floating point variable called tas (i.e, surface air temperature):

- each variable point has a size of 4 bytes;
- the ncells dimension is 20,971,520;
- the time dimension spans from 00:00 to 23:45 with a time frequency set at 15 minutes (i.e, 96 timesteps/day).

In particular, for the strong scalability tests four files from the ICON model with a size of 4 GB were preliminary merged into a single NetCDF file with `ncrcat` NCO operator with a total size of about 16 GB compressed (31 GB uncompressed). In this way, the overall dataset includes four days.

The weak scalability tests are performed by doubling both the file size and the number of processes. To do that, a subset of the previous file is used from 0,5 GB to 16 GB (a single day of data has been splitted using the `ncks` NCO operator). In the case of the second goal, the tests have been scaled up to 4 nodes considering data from 0,5 GB up to 64 GB compressed (124 GB uncompressed).

Results

Figure 7 shows the strong scalability test results comparing the Ophidia `IMPORTNC + ESDM` operator (blue line in the graph) and the Ophidia `IMPORTESDM` operator (orange line). For this test, the execution time has been measured by increasing the parallelism exploited by the Ophidia framework from 1 to 32 cores on a single compute node using the same file for each configuration.

As it can be observed from the figure, the use of the NetCDF-ESDM library is in all cases of the presented scenario is faster than the approach with the ESDM API.

Figure 7: Strong scalability results from the comparison of the Ophidia import operators using the NetCDF-ESDM library versus the use of the ESDM API.

Figure 8: Weak scalability results from the comparison of the Ophidia import operators using the NetCDF-ESDM library versus the use of the ESDM API.

Figure 8, instead, shows the results of the weak scalability tests for the same comparison: the Ophidia IMPORTNC + ESDM operator (blue line) versus the IMPORTESDM operator (orange line). In this case the execution time is measured by doubling both the data size and the number of processing elements (from 1 to 32) on a single node. As it can be observed from the graph, the IMPORTNC is also in this case faster than the IMPORTESDM in all configurations. The lower execution time measured in both cases while using the NetCDF-ESDM library could be related to internal optimizations performed by the ESDM developers when extending the NetCDF library, which were not carried out to the same extent in the Ophidia ESDM-based operators.

Concerning the second goal of the experimental evaluation, Figure 9 shows the results of the comparison between the usual Ophidia approach - implying a two-step process consisting of (i) loading data first (i.e., OPH_IMPORTESDM2 - yellow bars) and then (ii) applying the operation (i.e., OPH_REDUCE - green bars) - and the use of the in-flight extensions during data loading (i.e., via the OPH_IMPORTESDM2 operator shown by the orange bars). The standard deviation analytical kernels were used for these tests.

The results for the strong scalability tests are displayed, by increasing the number of cores from 1 to 32 on a single compute node while maintaining the data size constant. As it can be observed in the histogram, the use of the in-flight extensions during data loading (i.e., the IMPORT IN-FLIGHT) is in all cases faster than the two-step approach (i.e., IMPORT and REDUCE), similarly to what is shown in the preliminary results in (Heidmann et al., 2022). Moreover, as it can also be observed in the figure, the use of the in-flight import was in all cases even faster than the load time of input NetCDF data alone.

The same conditions are also applied for the weak scalability tests involving the IMPORTESDM plus the REDUCE operators and the IMPORT IN-FLIGHT, but in this case, the number of cores is increased (from 1 to 128) scaling from one node to four compute nodes. The results of this comparison are shown in Figure 10. The use of the in-flight kernel during data loading (i.e., the IMPORT IN-FLIGHT - orange bar) was always faster than the other approach for data reduction. More details can be found in Table 1, which shows also the data size besides the execution times of the two tests.

Figure 9: Strong scalability results of the comparison between the Ophidia traditional approach for data reduction and the approach based on in-flight data analysis.

Figure 10: Weak scalability results of the comparison between the Ophidia traditional approach for data reduction and the approach based on in-flight data analysis.

Table 1: Results from the weak scalability test comparing the Ophidia traditional approach for data reduction and the approach based on in-flight data analysis.

Number of nodes	Number of threads	Data Size [GB]	IMPORT + REDUCE Average time [s]	IMPORT IN-FLIGHT Average time [s]
1	1	0,96	8,26	5,06
1	2	1,9	8,98	5,81
1	4	3,8	9,53	5,91
1	8	7,6	10,39	7,20
1	16	15	11,02	7,70
1	32	31	14,09	11,11
2	64	61	18,33	14,35
4	128	121	21,77	17,59

4.3.3 Ophidia Summary

During the project several efforts have been undertaken to extend the Ophidia framework with the aim to provide better support for state-of-the-art ESM (e.g., non-regular gridded data) and improve the I/O performance. Moreover, the framework setup process has been simplified and made more portable thanks to the integration with Spack.

In terms of data management, different extensions have been explored for providing full parallel I/O to NetCDFv4 datasets, integrating the framework with novel storage solutions (i.e., ESDM) and supporting in-flight/in-transit analysis.

In this respect, the experimental evaluation performed has shown interesting results. Integration with the NetCDF API with support for ESDM (i.e., NetCDF-ESDM) not only resulted in being quicker and simpler but also produced a slightly faster execution time. The second set of tests showed that the use of the in-flight analytical kernels visibly reduces the execution time with respect to the current approach exploited in the Ophidia framework. These results, although the developments represent mainly a proof of concept, are very promising and will be taken into consideration in the project development roadmap.

4.4 CDO

CDO (Schulzweida, 2022) is a collection of command line Operators to manipulate and analyse Climate and NWP model data. Supported data formats are GRIB 1/2, netCDF 3/4, SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG. There are more than 600 operators available. It is developed at MPI-M for many years, and supported by the German Climate Computing Centre DKRZ. For a more elaborate description of the CDOs in the context of work package 5 of ESiWACE2 please refer to deliverable D5.2 (Heidmann et al., 2022). As announced there, here we will give a more detailed description of the target systems we developed for as well as the methods we applied, including benchmarks. The usefulness of gpu acceleration for a - field based - tool like CDOs will be discussed, and, where necessary, bottlenecks described.

Due to the current state of the HPC landscape we were only able to test the GPU accelerated routines on the DKRZ system Levante. On all other systems where we tried to gain access to we were notified that their GPU nodes were not operational yet. On Levante we were able to run the new implementation of the `lowpass` operator which uses FFTs to filter unwanted frequencies over the time steps of a data set.

4.4.1 Development Environment Experiences

Due to Levante being a newly setup system we found the software stack to be a lot more up-to-date than previously on Mistral. While the swap from the previous DKRZ system, Mistral, to the current one, Levante, caused heaps of issues and required some sections to be re-implemented, the overall experience was a lot more streamlined and less error prone due to the new options provided by the mostly up-to-date software stack. Several complex configurations could be completely scraped and replaced by simple configure calls. Some errors that required deeper knowledge of the setup on Mistral also vanished completely and made development much easier. The NVHPC compiler provided everything we needed for CUDA (NVIDIA et al., 2022) and OpenACC and as such also for usage of the CUFFT library all while having a lot less complications that stopped CDO from compiling. Thus we want to highlight the importance of an up-to-date software stack for using GPU acceleration or any high performance related tasks. We are aware that newly released software can cause problems as well, but this time it worked. Over time the use of GPUs should become even more streamlined and more accessible for non-programmers. Currently the process of using the new routines requires CDO to be compiled specifically for the present hardware. With the older software stack it would have been unfeasible to expect users to compile their own CDO. Even with the changes to the software stack and in turn the simplification of the compilation process, we recommend to the software stack maintainers of the respective sites to provide the required CDO installations for the hardware installed at their side.

4.4.2 Using GPU-Acceleration with CDO

To use the newly implemented routines or any future routine we added the `--enable_gpu` option for CDO. Currently the GPU features are not used by default and need to be requested specifically via the mentioned option. If multiple variants of an algorithm are present, we decided to always use the GPU implementation if `--enable_gpu` was used. For the future we envision a more specific method of enabling these features on a operator per operator basis. To build CDO with the GPU accelerations the following command is sufficient for the configuration of CDO:

```
./configure CXX="nvc++ -O3 -acc -std=c++17 -target=gpu -Minfo -fortranlibs" \
LDLFLAGS="-lcufft -lcudart" --with-proj --with-netcdf --with-fftw3 --enable-cuda
```

Listing 2: Configure call for CDO with CUDA FFTW implementation.

This allows to use ACC routines as well as CUDA and the contained CUFFT library. The only requirement is that a modern version of NVHPC is installed and used. This was tested and done on Levante with NVPVC 22.5 using GCC 11.2 as the backend of NVHPC. If these routines are not required CDO can still be compiled without NVHPC and with regular compilers like Clang and GCC.

4.4.3 CDO-CUFFT

The lowpass operator already supplied two variants for filtering frequencies in a data set. The first variant was a CDO intrinsic algorithm while the second make use of the FFTW library (Frigo and Johnson, 2005) to obtain the same goal. In this project we added another, third variant which uses a CUDA implementation of the FFTW library, see listing below.

For our benchmarks we choose the grid size and the number of time steps as our variables. In our tests we could show speedups of up to 40%. We could also show that our routine scales with the number of time steps instead of the grid size. This was expected for the routine as it transposes the data set to then apply die Fourier Transform on the time series instead of the grid. Surprising to see was that the size of the grid has a negative impact on the scaling. In our tests we saw that the speedup was reduced with each successive increase of the grid size. For grid-sizes larger than 2000 x 1000 with 10000 time steps we already ran into limitations in context of default RAM (512 GB) availability on our nodes.

Figure 11: Results lowpass CDO operator with different grid sizes and timesteps.

Figure 12: Results lowpass CDO speedups in context of number of timesteps.

4.4.4 Interpolation-Routine

Due to the switch from Mistral to Levante a previously working version of the GPU implementation of the CDO vertical interpolation routine now crashes when executed. Due to unplanned absences and the corresponding missing work hours in addition to Levante and other HPC systems late entry into service we were not able to get a working routine in time for this document.

4.4.5 Additional Changes to CDO

In addition to the routines we also adapted the build system of CDO. For GPU acceleration specific compilers are required. Building the whole program with these is an option but we wanted to be able to only compile the CUDA files with the NVHPC compiler while using for example Clang or GCC for the rest of CDO. Being able to do this minimizes the effects of compiler differences which can be quite substantial. Further we completely reworked the CDO test environment, while we were waiting for Levante to be fully available. In regard to maintainability and changeability of CDO these changes will prove extremely useful when larger revisions are executed, like adapting CDO to a more GPU friendly architecture. While the re-implementation of the test environment had a minimal impact on the ESiWACE2 project, aside of being able to more easily check if our changes had negative effects on the results, we strongly believe that the changes will contribute heavily to preparing CDO for future developments.

4.4.6 Applicability of GPU acceleration

In the general context of CDO we found that most routines do not allow for GPU acceleration. CDO is designed to work on a record per record basis. That means each data set is loaded in small chunks which are in most cases too small to justify the use of GPUs: the overhead caused by copying the data from the general memory to the GPU memory outweighs the shorter computation time. Furthermore, CDO operators are

implemented in a way that makes restructuring very time consuming. The restructuring would be necessary to combine multiple steps inside an operator into a larger block. With these larger blocks a small percentage of CDOs operators could be adapted for GPU acceleration. While such a restructuring is part of the long-term vision for CDO, the actual implementation would require very substantial changes to multiple core components of CDO. Another approach discussed was to buffer records until a sufficiently large amount of data was present and to then apply the calculations. But with the ever increasing size of data sets the size of each record increases, too. This in context with CDOs internal structure would lead to memory management issues. More concrete the buffering would have huge impact on the feasibility of running multiple operators in a single CDO command. One of CDOs core benefits is the chaining of operators. With the buffering and the fact that a newly calculated record needs to be saved in memory and that each operator has its own buffer for a single record, further buffering of multiple records per operator would lead to out of memory issues very fast. All in all this would mean even if we rebuild CDO to accommodate the requirements for GPU acceleration.

4.4.7 CDO Summary

In the time of this project we were able to identify 2 routines within CDO that have huge potential in context of GPU acceleration. Most other routines were found to have limited prospects for speedup gains due to the fact that CDO handles data transfers mostly on a record by record basis. This architecture does not allow for GPU acceleration since the records do not have the required size for GPU routines to outperform their inherent initial slowdown when transferring data from cpu memory to GPU memory. One of the mentioned routines was extended with a GPU implementation. This extension provides speedups of up to 40% depending on the size of the grid. The second routine could not be implemented in time frame of ESiWACE2. In general CDO and its build system have been updated to handle the required tools for GPU acceleration. In the context of these changes we found that older systems, or ,more specifically, systems with older software stacks have huge impact on the feasibility of distributing GPU routines to the wider community.

4.5 ParaView and online analysis

ParaView⁵ is the defacto-standard for interactive 3D rendering and analysis of large datasets. It is an open-source (BSD3) software developed by Kitware Inc and comes with builtin netCDF support for a range of standard data layouts. For several years, DKRZ has developed and maintained a reader for the ICON model output based on the Climate Data Interface (CDI) library (the backend of the CDOs and some variants of the ICON model output). In the course of ESiWACE2, DKRZ has extended the **Paraview CDI reader** to be more generic and enable the loading of arbitrary cell-based grids, given a matching grid file is provided. This allows ParaView now to also load the output of the other ESiWACE2 flagship models, as shown in figure 6 of D5.2 (Heidmann et al., 2022).

To ensure the sustainability of our developments and make them available to the community, these developments have been merged into the main branch of ParaView, and will be part of future ParaView releases available for download via <https://www.paraview.org/download/>, thus ensuring sustainability of the developments beyond the project lifespan of ESiWACE2. As described in ESiWACE2 Deliverable D4.1 (Bethke et al., 2021), ParaView can read data from ESDM by simply injecting the ESDM libnetcdf via LD_PRELOAD. In the context of **online data analysis with ParaView Catalyst**, we have first evaluated the direct in-situ approach. In this approach, the control flow is passed from the model computation to the visualization application. While the approach showed good performance with an added cost of roughly 1% for simple analysis or visualization tasks, and opens the path for providing all model fields to the visualization code, it also means that the whole model process set of up to several hundred thousand cores has to collaborate to render one image. To obtain a more sustainable solution, we decided to use the YAC coupler, developed at DKRZ ⁶, and used in the ICON model, as the interface to the model. As a coupler, YAC is designed to

⁵see: <https://paraview.org/>

⁶see: <https://dkrz-sw.gitlab-pages.dkrz.de/yac/>

transfer fields between different model components in an MPI MPMD setting, subsetting and remapping on the fly as desired. For this coupling, we developed YAVIZ (Yet Another VisualiZation Interface) as an interface between YAC and ParaView Catalyst. Attaching ParaView Catalyst via YAC for in-transit visualization and analysis has several major advantages over classic in-situ approaches.

- The coupler provides a clean interface, separating any development on the online analysis from development of the core model.
- By providing component parallelism, we can optimally exploit the extreme parallelism of current and upcoming supercomputers.
- With heterogeneous jobs, the visualization software can be run on different hardware platforms than the simulation code itself, allowing better exploitation of upcoming specialized hardware solutions.
- With the built-in subsetting and remapping support of YAC, we can pass reduced data into ParaView Catalyst, drastically reducing computational costs for handling of data on the backside of Earth or avoiding the processing of scales much smaller than a pixel in the visualization.

YAVIZ⁷ is an MPI-parallel C++ program that links to the YAC library and to the Catalyst library of ParaView. For YAC, it specifies which data fields are required on which grid. Structured grids are supported with a simple syntax, unstructured grids can be read from netCDF. For ParaView, it also defines the grid, deals with the 180° line in lat/lon setups, and can tetrahedralize datasets for efficient volume rendering.

Figure 13: Python and Paraview are coupled to the ICON model via YAC. YAVIZ acts as an adaptor for YAC and Catalyst.

In the course of this effort, we have developed **python bindings for YAC**, opening the path for processing in-situ fields with python, and thus opening the path to in-situ analysis for the entire python universe, including many of the currently used machine learning approaches. As can be seen from Listing 3, only a minimal amount of actual code is necessary to obtain fields from the icon model. Further configurations for the coupler currently are provided via YAC's XML configuration file. We have merged these python bindings into the main branch of YAC and are currently working on providing API calls for the configuration of YAC as well. Together with various usability-improvements for passing many fields between different components, these additions will form the main changes for the upcoming YAC 3.0 release. We are planning to continue

⁷see: <https://gitlab.dkrz.de/k202160/yaviz>

the developments of the in-situ coupling via YAC and the Python interface in the BMBF project WarmWorld. A simple example for an in-situ python script can be found in Listing 3.

```
1 from yac import *
2 import numpy as np
3
4 yac = YAC()
5 yac.def_datetime("2030-01-01T00:00:00", "2040-01-00T00:00:00")
6 comp = yac.def_comp(f"YAC In-situ component")
7
8 # Create a global 100x50 grid on which to request the data
9 x = np.linspace(-np.pi,np.pi,100)
10 y = np.linspace(-0.5*np.pi,0.5*np.pi,50)
11 grid = Reg2dGrid(f"latlon", x, y)
12
13 points = grid.def_points(Location.CORNER, x, y) # register the grid with yac
14
15 field = Field.create("tas", comp, points, 1, "1") # register tas as field.
16 # The details of the remap currently are defined in YAC's XML configuration file.
17
18 yac.search()
19
20 while True:
21     data, info = field.get() # data contains the field data
22     plot_or_analyze(data)
23     if info == 4: # indicating last get operation
24         break
```

Listing 3: Example code for an in-situ visualization or analysis python script using YAC. Receiving the field `tas` from remote processes.

When talking with the climate scientists using the high-resolution ICON model at MPI-M, we learned that their main interest was in writing subsampled / remapped data to disk for later plotting and analysis, as this maintains flexibility, while for pre-rendered images, a change in the perspective or color palette would require a re-run of the high-resolution model. Therefore, in a collaboration with the H2020 project nextGEMS, we are currently exploring the use of the YAC python interface in combination with zarr files for providing multiple resolutions of the model output, allowing the users semantic data access via intake-esm to the resolution that's best suited for their analysis and plotting needs.

4.5.1 Summary

We have established YAC as the centerpiece of our online data analysis approaches. We have extended it with Python bindings, and can now apply python analysis codes as online analysis to the ICON model, or any other model with YAC bindings. These changes have been merged back into the main branch of YAC, so they are going to be available to all users in the future. Furthermore, we have developed YAVIZ, a ParaView Catalyst interface for YAC, allowing for online 3D rendering and data analysis. For the use of ParaView with data stored on disk, we have extended the CDI reader developed by DKRZ to support arbitrary grids, so it can now handle all ESiWACE models. These developments along with better support for various output file variants and other features have been merged back into the main branch of ParaView and will thus be sustained and disseminated to all ParaView users in the future.

4.6 Summary and Lessons Learnt

In the course of WP5, several developments have been carried out with the goal of improving the toolchain for handling data post-processing, analytics and visualisation. The Ophidia framework has been extended to also support non-regular grids, thus being able to address a wider range of ESM simulation data, such as those from the ESiWACE2 flagship models, as well as to provide better support for parallel I/O over NetCDFv4 dataset (based on HDF5). Moreover, the integration with novel storage middlewares (e.g., ESDM) and the use of in-flight analytics kernels in the framework (with more than 30 kernels implemented) has also been performed. The results from the integration activities allowed us to revise and improve the code for future similar extensions and also provided hints for the development roadmap. In the context of GPU kernels, we enhanced CDO to enable GPU acceleration in general, and upgraded selected operators to use the newly established features. For this, we analysed the operators of CDO, which contain many that are not suitable to be accelerated by GPU use, and a few possible candidates for acceleration. We also used this opportunity to map out the future of CDO and the changes to the code required for enabling more and better accelerated routines. For ParaView, we added support for arbitrary grids and evaluated in-situ and in-transit coupling to the ICON model. Additionally, we extended the YAC coupler with python bindings, and thus created a general-purpose interface to the model variables with integrated remapping and temporal aggregation. In the context of this work, some lessons consistently reappeared, so we consider them as noteworthy for future efforts in similar directions.

- **Build on interfaces well-established in the community to support the use of novel solutions:** integration with new infrastructures and system can be simplified if standard interfaces are used. By providing and using ESDM's netCDF interface, we made it very easy to switch Ophidia, ParaView and CDO to ESDM. Other tools, even those where the source code is not available, could also be 'migrated' by injecting a patched netCDF library via LD_PRELOAD.
- **Provide high-level Python-based libraries.** The climate and weather community is following the general trend in eScience towards the adoption of very high-level languages such as Python and GUIs like Jupyter Notebooks. The ecosystem of Python modules and libraries developed specifically for Earth science is, in fact, continuously growing. Being able to provide solutions which can be used within this ecosystem can further foster the adoption of tools by new generation of scientists. Providing python bindings for YAC, the ESM-D-PAV and improving those already made available, such as for Ophidia, goes in the direction of widening the user base that could benefit from the project developments.
- **Exploration of new data management approaches to cope with larger scale ESM data.** As the size of ESM data grows, it becomes essential to explore different methodologies for accessing and processing data. The work done in Ophidia to support parallel I/O (with multi-threads) on NetCDFv4 data and, in particular, the extensions to run simple analytical kernels while data is being loaded from the storage to the compute nodes target these needs. The evolution of scientific platforms, however, requires a high effort, even simply to develop a proof of concept, especially when targeting new (not yet established) approaches and technologies. Funding from research projects is thus vital to support the exploration of innovative solutions for scientific analysis towards extreme scale data.
- **Integration of GPU acceleration into old code bases faces huge barriers** Older software is rarely suitable for easy integration of GPU kernels. The requirements like huge amounts of operations over a large data set partly would result in substantial restructuring of the code not fitting the resources provided by projects like this. For future software development projects we learned that a general restructuring of algorithms into specific phases, (init, run, single step, finalize) can and will help merging multiple operations together: this would make it easier then to fulfil the requirements of GPU acceleration.
- **Build on, and extend existing codes with a solid (long-term) support base.** Users will be very hesitant to re-design their workflow for tools that are only funded for a short time through a project. On

the other hand, extending/improving existing, and well-supported tools is something where a project can provide a valuable impulse. With Ophidia, CDO, YAC and ParaView we built on pre-existing systems that have a clear place, attention and value in the community and institutional backing for long-term support.

- **Build modular systems**, so there still is a clear benefit even if users are not interested or able to use your complete toolchain. While CDO, Ophidia, and ParaView can be used in the context of ESDM-PAV, most of our developments can be used in the context of ESiWACE3, where ESDM will be replaced by ECMWF's FDB. This applies to the GPU use in CDO, the improved grid support in Ophidia and ParaView, as well as the in-situ work, that is completely independent of ESDM. It is also noteworthy, that the minor changes required for the integration with ESDM system (when needed, as in the case of Ophidia) prepared the software for an easier integration with similar storage systems.

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6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Following the project 3 months extension, this deliverable has been postponed by 1 month from December 2022 to January 2023 in order to provide for more time for completing the experimental evaluation of the

key developments. Unfortunately, running tests on EuroHPC systems was still not possible due to delays in setting up and providing access to these systems. A test of the complete software stack including ESDM was not yet possible, see D4.2. Nevertheless, all interfaces to ESDM from the extensions developed here are publicly available as open source code.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

As part of the European Strategies for HPC, our work focused on the improvement of the toolchains in weather and climate modeling and in particular those aspects related to post-processing, analytics and visualisation. In this way, we readied ourselves for the vast amounts of data, that storm-resolving climate simulations produce, as well as for the use of heterogeneous computing infrastructures. The key results supporting this goal can be summarised as:

- Ophidia can now support non-regular (unstructured) grids, common in next generation weather and climate models (e.g., ICON, IFS).
- The CDI reader of ParaView now supports grids with arbitrary numbers of vertices per cell (e.g. IFS, FESOM, DYNAMICO) in addition to the traditional ICON support.
- CDO now supports use of GPUs for specific routines, and is ready to be used in the complete toolchain
- All of these tools can be used together in processing pipelines within the common ESDM-PAV framework.
- CDO, ParaView and now also Ophidia can be installed on different architectures through the Spack package manager (Budich et al., 2022).
- Online analysis support via YAC now allows to analyze data without even writing it to disk. Python and ParaView are explicitly supported as analysis tools.

8 Sustainability

Our efforts were focused on well-established software, which will be supported beyond the lifetime of the ESiWACE2 project. All changes to Ophidia, CDO, YAC and ParaView have been merged into the softwares' main development branches, and will thus be available for future use independent of project funding. Such, they will benefit projects like ACROSS, DestinE, nextGEMS, or EERIE. The in-situ analysis efforts will be continued in the German BMBF project WarmWorld. Moreover, the developments and the lessons learnt related to data analytics with the Ophidia platform will be further exploited and improved in the context of projects such as the EuroHPC eFlows4HPC and ESiWACE3.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We mainly extended existing and well-established software packages. Thus, these changes will spread in the community as new software versions are rolled out across compute centers.

As for other deliverables from the project, this document will publicly be made available on Zenodo.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See Table 2.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

See Table 3.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

All developments are openly accessible as Open Source codes.

Appendices

```

1 from esdm_pav_client import Workflow, Experiment
2 experiment = Experiment(
3     name="Cold spell",
4     author="ESiWACE2",
5     abstract="Perform the computation of Cold Spell indexes using ESDM PAV",
6     exec_mode="sync")
7 t0 = experiment.newTask(name="Create climatological mean",
8     type="CDO",
9     operator='-ydaymean -runavg,5 -mergetime',
10    arguments={'input': '/path/to/cmip6/tasmin/past/*.nc',
11              'output': '/path/to/temporary/climatological_mean.nc'})
12 t1 = experiment.newTask(name="Create container",
13     type="ophidia",
14     operator='oph_createcontainer',
15     on_error='skip',
16     arguments={'container': 'coldspell',
17               'dim': 'lat|lon|time',
18               'dim_type': 'double|double|double',
19               'hierarchy': 'oph_base|oph_base|oph_time'})
20 t2 = experiment.newTask(name="Import climatological mean",
21     type="ophidia",
22     operator='oph_importnc2',
23     arguments={'measure': 'tasmin',
24               'container': 'coldspell',
25               'import_metadata': 'yes',
26               'imp_dim': 'time',
27               'imp_concept_level': 'd',
28               'description': 'Min temperature climatological mean'},
29     dependencies={t0:'input', t1:''})
30 tf0 = experiment.newTask(name="Begin parallel for",
31     type="control",
32     operator='for',
33     arguments={'input': '[/path/to/cmip6/tasmin/future/*.nc]',
34               'key': 'source',
35               'parallel': 'yes'},
36     dependencies={t1:''})
37 tf1 = experiment.newTask(name="Import",
38     type="ophidia",
39     operator='oph_importnc2',
40     arguments={'input': '@source',
41               'measure': 'tasmin',
42               'container': 'coldspell',
43               'import_metadata': 'yes',
44               'imp_dim': 'time',
45               'imp_concept_level': 'd',
46               'description': 'Max temperature in current year'},
47     dependencies={tf0:''})
48 tf2 = experiment.newTask(name="Intercube",
49     type="ophidia",
50     operator='oph_intercube',
51     arguments={'description': 'Result from intercube'},
52     dependencies={tf1:'cube', t2:'cube2'})
53 tf3 = experiment.newTask(name="Apply",
54     type="ophidia",
55     operator='oph_apply',
56     arguments={'query': "oph_predicate('OPH_INT','OPH_INT', oph_sequence('OPH_INT',\
57               'OPH_INT',oph_predicate('OPH_FLOAT','OPH_INT', oph_predicate('OPH_FLOAT',\

```

```

58             'OPH_FLOAT', measure,'x-1000', '>0', '0', 'x'), 'x+5', '<0', '1', '0'), \
59             'length', 'yes'), 'x-5', '>0', 'x', '0')",
60             'description': 'Cold Spell Duration cube'},
61         dependencies={tf2:'cube'})
62 t3 = experiment.newTask(name="End parallel for",
63                         type="control",
64                         operator='endfor',
65                         arguments={},
66                         dependencies={tf3:'cube'})
67 t4 = experiment.newTask(name="Merge",
68                         type="ophidia",
69                         operator='oph_mergecubes',
70                         arguments={'mode': 'a',
71                                   'hold_values': 'yes',
72                                   'order': 'source'},
73                         dependencies={t3:'cubes'})
74 t5 = experiment.newTask(name="Reduce",
75                         type="ophidia",
76                         operator='oph_reduce2',
77                         arguments={'operation': 'max',
78                                   'dim': 'time',
79                                   'description': 'Cold Spell Duration Index cube'},
80                         dependencies={t4:'cube'})
81 t5e = experiment.newTask(name="Export CSD",
82                          type="ophidia",
83                          operator='oph_exportnc2',
84                          arguments={'output': '/path/to/temporary/CSD.nc'},
85                          dependencies={t5:'cube'})
86 t5v = experiment.newTask(name="Visualise CSD",
87                          type="generic",
88                          operator='/path/to/script/visualize.sh',
89                          arguments={},
90                          dependencies={t5e:'input'})
91 t6 = experiment.newTask(name="Apply for CSN",
92                          type="ophidia",
93                          operator='oph_apply',
94                          arguments={'query': "oph_predicate('OPH_INT', 'OPH_INT',measure,'x', '>0', '1', '0')",
95                                    'description': 'Apply for CSN cube'},
96                          dependencies={t4:'cube'})
97 t7 = experiment.newTask(name="Reduce for CSN",
98                          type="ophidia",
99                          operator='oph_reduce2',
100                         arguments={'operation': 'sum',
101                                   'dim': 'time',
102                                   'description': 'Cold Spell Number cube'},
103                         dependencies={t6:'cube'})
104 t7e = experiment.newTask(name="Export CSN",
105                          type="ophidia",
106                          operator='oph_exportnc2',
107                          arguments={'output': '/path/to/temporary/CSN.nc'},
108                          dependencies={t7:'cube'})
109 t7v = experiment.newTask(name="Visualise CSN",
110                          type="generic",
111                          operator='/path/to/script/visualize.sh',
112                          arguments={},
113                          dependencies={t7e:'input'})
114 t8 = experiment.newTask(name="Reduce for CSF",
115                          type="ophidia",
116                          operator='oph_reduce2',
117                          arguments={'operation': 'sum',
118                                    'dim': 'time',

```

```

119         'description': 'Reduce for CSF cube'},
120     dependencies={t4:'cube'})
121 t9 = experiment.newTask(name="Apply for CSF",
122     type="ophidia",
123     operator='oph_apply',
124     arguments={'query': "oph_mul_scalar('OPH_INT','OPH_FLOAT',measure, "+ str(1/365) +)"",
125         'description': 'Cold Spell Frequency cube'},
126     dependencies={t8:'cube'})
127 t9e = experiment.newTask(name="Export CSF",
128     type="ophidia",
129     operator='oph_exportnc2',
130     arguments={'output': '/path/to/temporary/CSF.nc'},
131     dependencies={t9:'cube'})
132 t9v = experiment.newTask(name="Visualise CSF",
133     type="generic",
134     operator='/path/to/script/visualize.sh',
135     arguments={},
136     dependencies={t9e:'input'})
137 workflow = Workflow(experiment)
138 workflow.submit()
139 workflow.monitor(frequency=1, iterative=True, visual_mode=True)

```

Listing 4: PAV Pipeline for the “cold spell” computation

```

1 from esdm_pav_client import Workflow, Experiment
2 experiment = Experiment(
3     name="Iterative processing",
4     author="CMCC",
5     abstract="Perform an iterative computation over an ESDM container",
6     exec_mode="sync")
7 t1 = experiment.newTask(name="Loop",
8     type="control",
9     operator='for',
10    arguments={'key': 'index',
11        'counter': '1:100'})
12 t2 = experiment.newTask(name="Set",
13     type="control",
14     operator='set',
15     arguments={'key': 'start|stop|previous',
16        'value': 'EVAL((&index-1)*10)|EVAL(&index*10-1)|@CUBE'},
17     dependencies={t1:'cube'})
18 t3 = experiment.newTask(name="Wait",
19     type="control",
20     operator='wait',
21     arguments={'type': 'file',
22        'output': 'esdm://etas.nc',
23        'measure': 'tas',
24        'subset_dims': 'time',
25        'subset_filter': '@stop',
26        'time_filter': 'no',
27        'timeout': '10'},
28     dependencies={t2:''})
29 t4 = experiment.newTask(name="If the first loop",
30     type="control",
31     operator='if',
32     arguments={'condition': '&index=1'},
33     dependencies={t3:'input'})
34 t5 = experiment.newTask(name="Import operation",

```

```

35         type="ophidia",
36         operator='oph_importesdm2',
37         arguments={'measure': 'tas',
38                   'subset_dims': 'time',
39                   'subset_filter': '@start_1:stop',
40                   'time_filter': 'no',
41                   'operation': 'stat',
42                   'args': '11'},
43         dependencies={t4:'input'})
44 t6 = experiment.newTask(name="Else (next loops)",
45                         type="control",
46                         operator='else',
47                         arguments={},
48                         dependencies={t4:'input'})
49 t7 = experiment.newTask(name="Concat operation",
50                         type="ophidia",
51                         operator='oph_concatesdm2',
52                         arguments={'measure': 'tas',
53                                   'subset_dims': 'time',
54                                   'subset_filter': '@start_1:stop',
55                                   'time_filter': 'no',
56                                   'operation': 'stat',
57                                   'args': '11',
58                                   'cube': '@previous'},
59                         dependencies={t6:'input'})
60 t8 = experiment.newTask(name="End if",
61                         type="control",
62                         operator='endif',
63                         arguments={},
64                         dependencies={t5:'cube', t7:'cube'})
65 t9 = experiment.newTask(name="End loop",
66                         type="control",
67                         operator='endfor',
68                         arguments={},
69                         dependencies={t8:'cube'})
70 t10 = experiment.newTask(name="Export",
71                          type="ophidia",
72                          operator="oph_exportesdm2",
73                          arguments={'output': 'esdm://output.nc',
74                                    'force': 'yes'},
75                          dependencies={t9:'cube'})
76 workflow = Workflow(experiment)
77 workflow.submit()
78 workflow.monitor(frequency=1, iterative=True, visual_mode=True)

```

Listing 5: PAV Pipeline for the “iterative processing” use case

Table 2: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Talk	In-situ analyses and visualization of large climate model data	Oct 16, 2022 IEEE VIS 2022 - Oklahoma City	scientific audience / visualization community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7375384	100
Training Event	Third training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation	Sep 6 - Sep 9, 2022, Online	Scientific audience	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-training-2022	24
Talk	Towards HPC and Big Data convergence for climate analysis at scale	May 9-11, 2022, Barcelona	Scientific audience	https://zenodo.org/record/6783441	80
Training Event	Second training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation	Sep 13 - Sep 16, 2021, Online	Scientific audience	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/training-on-high-performance-data-analytics-and-visualisation	33
Training Event	Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation	Oct 6 - Nov 3, 2020, Online	Scientific audience	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-training-2020/hpda-training-2020	40

Table 3: Publications related to this deliverable

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Submitted	Towards HPC and Big Data Analytics Convergence: Design and Experimental Evaluation of a HPDA Framework for eScience at Scale	D. Elia, S. Fiore and G. Aloisio	IEEE Access	yes